

Developing User-Centred Approaches to Technological Innovation in Literary Translation (DUAL-T)

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Rationale

Recent years have seen a growing research interest on the application of translation technology to literary translation workflows, mostly in the form of Machine Translation (MT) or post-editing of MT output. In these studies, literary translators' voices are virtually absent. This project addresses the discrepancy between research in Computer Science/AI and Translation Studies, as well as the absence of literary translators from the conversation surrounding technological innovation in their profession. It does so by proactively integrating literary translators' input in the co-creation of a new technology-inclusive workflow.

Research Questions

The project was guided by the following research questions:

1. How do overall translation time and time spent outside of the tool differ between the three translation workflows?
2. How does the number of keystrokes differ between the three translation workflows?
3. How does cognitive effort differ between the three translation workflows?
4. What are translators' attitudes towards text segmentation in the three workflows?
5. Does perceived effort match measured effort?
6. What aspects of each workflow do literary translators like and/or dislike, and which ones would they like to see in an ideal workflow?

Workflows

Twenty-four professional literary translators were asked to translate three short stories of around 300 words each from English into Dutch, using three different workflows:

WF01: Microsoft Word;

WF02: Trados Studio 2022;

WF03: a proprietary Machine Translation Post-editing platform.

Texts

The three short stories were taken from the short story collection *One More Thing* by BJ Novak (2014). They were the following:

T01: *Rome*

T02: *The Beautiful Girl in the Bookstore*

T03: *They Kept Driving Faster and They Outrun the Rain*

Methodology

Data was collected from 24 professional literary translators between October 2023 and January 2024. User testing data was collected using keylogging and screen capturing. Inputlog 8.0.0.17 was used for keylogging, while OBS 30.2.3 was used for screen capturing. Participants had to fill in pre- and post-task questionnaires. After the translation tasks and the post-task questionnaire, a 30-minute interview was conducted with participants.

During the second phase of the project, two focus groups were conducted. Each focus group lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes.

Focus Group 1: 4 professional literary translators + 1 representative of the DUAL-T industry partner (book translation company that developed the proprietary tool used during the user testing phase of the project for the MTPE workflow).

Focus Group 2: 3 professional literary translators + 1 representative of the DUAL-T industry partner (book translation company that developed the proprietary tool used during the user testing phase of the project for the MTPE workflow).

The data repository

This data repository is hosted on Zenodo at [this link](#), and it contains the following:

- *DUAL-T User Testing Dataset:* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929161>
- *DUAL-T Pre- and Post-Task Questionnaires & Questionnaire Results:* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929385>
- *DUAL-T Interview Topic Guide:* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929455>
- *DUAL-T Focus Group Topic Guide:* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929479>